

University Policy Statement

ASD 17-57

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RETENTION OF FACULTY RIGHTS TO DEPOSIT AND DISSEMINATE THEIR SCHOLARLY ARTICLES: AN OPEN ACCESS POLICY

I. PREAMBLE

Reasons abound to pass an open access policy that protects faculty and retains faculty rights to deposit and disseminate their scholarly articles as they see fit. These reasons include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Faculty often unnecessarily sign away all copyright of their articles to publishers, when faculty can easily and collectively reserve those rights.
- Without such a policy, faculty who share articles on a publicly accessible website are technically in legal violation of most standard copyright agreements.
- Faculties across leading universities have adopted comparable open access policies to protect themselves and their articles.
- Articles deposited in open access repositories are read and cited more widely by scholars.
- The taxpayers, students, alumni, and donors who fund our public university deserve to have reliable and perpetual access to the articles written by our faculty.
- Open access articles help bridge the information divide between persons affiliated with wealthy institutions and the majority of the world’s population who lack such privilege.
- Unexpected people in many places will take inspiration from these articles and build upon them.
- Most governmental and non-governmental external grant funders have already adopted open access policies and require the deposit of grant funded articles in open access repositories.
- California State University, Fullerton, which strives to be a national model of public comprehensive higher education and a leader in the CSU system, would be the first CSU to adopt such a policy.
- The international reputation of our University and its faculty will grow together with the awareness and use of our faculty publications and university websites.
- Such a policy will give the University a legal basis to host and provide public access to faculty articles that have been accepted for publication.

40 II. GRANT OF LICENSE AND LIMITATIONS

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42 The faculty of California State University, Fullerton is committed to making their scholarly
43 articles widely and freely available in an open access repository. In keeping with that
44 commitment, each faculty member grants to California State University, Fullerton a
45 nonexclusive, irrevocable, worldwide license to exercise any and all rights under copyright
46 relating to each of his or her scholarly articles, in any medium, provided that the articles are not
47 sold for a profit, and to authorize others to do the same. Any other systematic uses of the licensed
48 articles by California State University, Fullerton (hereafter, “the University”) must be approved
49 by the Academic Senate. This policy does not transfer copyright ownership, which remains with
50 the faculty author, unless that author chooses to transfer it.

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52 III. SCOPE

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54 The policy applies to all scholarly articles authored or co-authored while the person is a member
55 of the faculty except for any articles completed before the adoption of this policy and any articles
56 for which the faculty member entered into an incompatible licensing or assignment agreement
57 before the adoption of this policy. This policy does not in any way prescribe or limit the venue of
58 publication. This policy neither requires nor prohibits the payment of fees or publication costs by
59 authors.

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61 IV. WAIVERS (OPT-OUT) AND EMBARGOES

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63 Upon express direction by a faculty member, the University will waive the license for a
64 particular article or delay access for a specified period of time.

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66 V. DEPOSIT

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68 The University commits to make the process as simple, flexible and automated as possible to
69 deposit articles in our institutional repository. Each faculty member will help the University
70 obtain an electronic copy of the final version of the article no later than the date of its first
71 publication, whether that publication be online or in print.

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73 VI. OVERSIGHT

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75 The Pollak Library will implement this policy. The Academic Senate Library Committee will
76 review the policy after three years and present a report to the faculty. Any changes to the text of
77 this policy will require approval by the Academic Senate.

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79 **Passed unanimously by University Library Senate Committee, March 20, 2017**